
FIGURES ATTRACT ATTENTION TO THE ISSUE OF INTERNET ADDICTION

Polumeeva I.*Saint-Petersburg University of Management Technologies and Economics*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10975184>**Abstract**

The article by Polumeeva I.N. considers the issue of the internet-addicted behavior and recognizing the pattern of internet-addiction, on the base on Chen Internet Addiction Scale, indicates the need to monitor and identify the components of behavior inherent in Internet addiction, draws attention to taking into consideration the importance of feedback from student's position.

Keywords: internet-addicted behavior, compulsive symptoms, withdrawal symptoms, tolerance scale, time management, feedback.

According to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), approximately 67% of the world's population is connected to the Internet by 2023. [1] The Internet has brought comfort and interest to our lives. Many of us do not notice how many times a day we turn to the Internet for various issues: from weather forecasting and route planning to searching for scientific literature. The research conducted by the Russian Public Opinion Research Center (VCIOM), showed that 74% of respondents under the age of 25 log into the global network every day, one in three spends more than four hours on the Internet daily, one in four believes that you need to be online all the time, so in 2018 it was 19%, in 2020 – 24%, and in 2023 – 25%. [2]

A group of students were asked to take a test aimed at identifying a pattern of Internet addiction with the help of Chen Internet Addiction Scale (CIAS). This technique reliably measured the severity of Internet addiction, the main advantage of this test is a symptomological and integrating structure that allows to identify the components of behavior typical for Internet-addicted behavior. CIAS includes five diagnostic scales:

- 1) The scale of compulsive symptoms (Com) – the feeling of being forced to stay in the Internet space, the desire to "enter the network";
- 2) The scale of withdrawal symptoms (Wit) – the level of discomfort that occurs during a long absence from the Internet;
- 3) Tolerance scale (Tol) – the level of stability of a person's connections with the Internet;
- 4) The scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH);

5) Time management Scale (TM) – the influence of the Internet on a daily routine.

There are also two types of supra-scale criteria – key symptoms of Internet addiction (IA-Sym), which include the first three scales (Com, Wit, Tol) and the criterion of negative consequences of Internet use (IARP), consisting of a scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems and a time management scale (IH, TM). The sum of all scales is an integral indicator of the presence of Internet-addicted behavior (CIAS Scale). $CIAS = Com + Wit + Tol + IH + TM$

The assessment according to the general indicator of the methodology:

from 27 points to 42 – the absence of Internet-addicted behavior;

from 43 points to 64 – propensity to develop Internet-addicted behavior/pre-addictive stage;

from 65 points and above, it is reasonably possible to state the presence of Internet-addicted behavior (behavior with a component of Internet abuse). [3] Due to the presence of five scales in this technique, it is possible not only to diagnose the presence or absence of Internet-addicted behavior, but also to determine the severity of symptoms characterizing the pattern of addicted behavior. As a result of the tests analysis, the respondents were divided into three groups: a group with a minimal risk of Internet-addicted behavior, let's call it Group A, with 13% according to the diagram; a group with a tendency to Internet-addicted behavior – Group B, with 68% and with a clearly defined pattern of Internet-addicted behavior Group C– 19%, the percentage is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Total CIAS assessment

Let's look at the indicators of the evaluation scales in each group. Figure 2 shows data in the group with the lowest risk of Internet- addicted behavior, group A.

Figure 2. Data in Group A.

Key symptoms of Internet addiction (IA-Sym): 23,5
 Negative consequences of Internet addiction (IA-RP): 17
 Total CIAS assessment: from 37 to 42

Analyzing the test data in group A, it can be concluded that the respondents have high scores on the intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH) scale, withdrawal symptoms scale (Wit), tolerance scale (Tol), compulsive symptoms scale (Com) and these scores are higher than the average values of the Chen scale. The highest indicator on the scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH), therefore,

it is possible that if a difficult life situation arises, this group of respondents has a risk of moving to group B. To prevent the occurrence of Internet addiction, correction of the coping strategy, timely seeking help, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle may be recommended.

Consider the values of the indicators on the main scales in group B (assessment of averages):

Figure 3. Data in Group B.

Key symptoms of Internet addiction (IA-Sym): 31,5

Negative consequences of Internet addiction (IA-RP): 20,7

Total CIAS assessment: от 43 до 64

This group turned out to be the largest. Analyzing the data in group B, we see that the respondents have indicators on the scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH), the scale of withdrawal symptoms (Wit) and the scale of compulsive symptoms (Com), the time management scale (TM) corresponding to the average values of the Chen scale for the group with a tendency to Internet addiction behavior. The index on the tolerance scale (Tol) exceeds the average on the Chen scale (9.5; 7.9). The value of this scale (Tol) indicates the presence of an already established stable

connection of the respondent with the Internet. High figures on the withdrawal symptoms scale (Wit) indicate a decrease in the respondents' ability to control time on the Internet. The combination of such indicators (Tol + Wit) prevents a decrease in consumption, increases the risk of moving to group C, which necessitates specialized care.

Move on to the indicators in group C (assessment of averages).

Figure 3. Data in Group C.

Key symptoms of Internet addiction (IA-Sym): 41,1

Negative consequences of Internet addiction (IA-RP): 31,8

Total CIAS assessment: from 65 and above.

The analysis of the data in group C showed that the values on the scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH), the scale of withdrawal symptoms (Wit), and the time management scale (TM) correspond to the average values of the Chen scale for the group with a clearly defined and stable pattern of Internet-addicted behavior. Indicators on the compulsive symptoms scale (Com) and on the tolerance scale (Tol) exceed the average value on the Chen scale (14.2; 13.5

and 13;11.7). Respondents in this group have the highest score on the scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH). Thus, the respondents in group C are characterized by reduced control over Internet-addicted behavior. The combination of scales of compulsive behavior and tolerance form maladaptive coping, in the form of withdrawal from reality and distancing via the Internet with an increase in psycho-emotional tension.

Such maladaptive coping hinders the harmonious development of personality and leads to impaired health at the bio-psycho-social level, which is reflected in high indicators on the scale of intrapersonal and health-related problems (IH). The respondents included in this group need qualified assistance for additional diagnosis and further psychotherapy.

Testing showed that 87% of respondents have an average and high level of Internet-addicted behavior, which is expressed in daily visits to the Internet, exceeding the amount of time planned for the network and neglecting intrapersonal problems and health. In order to prevent Internet-addicted behavior of students who took part in the testing, a conversation was held that increases their level of competence in Internet addiction issues. The majority of respondents are critical of their condition and have shown interest in this topic. Recognizing feedback as the most operational and important way for both the teacher and the student to improve the quality of communication allows conducting surveys and questionnaires. [4, p.63]

Based on the feedback from students and on the test results, the following recommendations can be identified for teachers working with these groups of students: 1. Raise students' awareness of Internet addic-

tion issues. 2. Reduce the level of classroom and homework assignments that require an Internet connection. 3. Include exercises in the lesson system aimed at reducing emotional stress and showing imagination.

References:

1. Facts and figures. Youth Internet use. URL:<https://www.itu.int/itu-d/reports/statistics/2023/10/10/ff23-internet-use/> (date of request: 04/07/2024)
2. VCIOM. News: Digital Detox — 2023: about using the Internet and taking a break from it. URL:<https://wciom.ru/analytical-reviews/analiticheskii-obzor/cifrovoy-detoks-2023-opolzovanii-internetom-i-otdykhe-ot-nego> (date of request: 03/23/2024).
3. Malygin V.L., Feklisov K.A., Iskandirova A.B., Antonenko A.A. Methodological approaches to early detection of Internet-dependent behavior. [Electronic resource] // Medical psychology in Russia: electronic scientific journal. 2011. N 6. URL: <http://mprj.ru> (date of request: 03/29/2024).
4. Polumeeva I. Teacher - student, how not to lose contact in distance learning. Polish Journal of Science. 2021 №40 ISSN: 3353-2389